

Analysis of Opinions on Issues Affecting Sex Ratio: A Case Study of Jalgaon District

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Abstract :

The present paper tries to analyze the opinions on issue affecting sex ratio in Jalgaon district of Maharashtra. The survey method is used for the study. About 900 respondents are interviewed from 30 villages from the district. Systematic random sampling method is used while selecting the respondents. It is found that a sizeable proportion of men are agree that household work should be shared by men. It is also interesting that many respondent still are unaware about biological fact that by birth girls are stronger than boys. When the mindset is such that women have to be subordinated, it will be a difficult task, if not impossible to confront it, to bring about any change. Though there are certain good changes happened in the society regarding empowerment of women and girl child but during the field visit, male respondents were vacillating regarding acceptance.

Keywords : opinion, sex ratio, Jalgaon district

Introduction:

Sex ratio is one of the important components of population composition of any region. The sex ratio is defined as the ratio of the number of males to number of females in a population set. It is internationally expressed per 100 females but in India, it is expressed as per 1000 males. In Maharashtra, the child sex ratio in the year 1991 was 946 girls for every 1000 boys and in 2001, it declined up to 913 girls per 1000 boys. But in 2011 Census, this decline is very sharp and it has become the matter of greater concerned because now this ratio is as low as 894 girls per thousand boys. In Jalgaon district, the sex ratio was only 822 females per thousand males. This is the matter of serious concerned. Biologically, there should not be difference in numbers of male and females. But this difference exists due to various socio-economic factors as well as customs, beliefs, taboos etc. prevailing in the society. It is important to understand why and how the child sex ratio has declined. Other things being equal, the child sex ratio, like the sex ratio at birth, does not undergo drastic changes over short periods of time. Women have experienced in the past, and continue to experience, higher mortality than men from late infancy to almost the end of their reproductive period. The various customs, beliefs, taboos prevailing in the society allow to discriminate between male and females. In many families females under-privileged due to these factors. Though, these customs are followed by the most of the people, but there exists difference of opinion among men, females and mother-in-laws. This paper tries to analyse the responses of people about the issue affecting sex ratio in Jalgaon district.

Objective:

The objective of the present research paper is to analyse the opinion on issue affecting sex ratio in Jalgaon district of Maharashtra.

Research Methodology:

The researcher undertook a study to ascertain the awareness about the existence of dowry system and dowry harassment in the study region. The field work was conducted throughout the district. The primary data for the study was collected through multi-stage stratified random sampling method. Two villages from each tehsils (15 x 2 = 30 villages) were selected by considering various geographical factors such as physiography, rainfall, net sown area, density of population and sex ratio. Urban respondent were considered from Amalner town. The perceptions of different stakeholders – women (15-45 years), men and mothers-in-law/elderly women, were ascertained. 10 women (15-45 years), 10 men and 10 mothers-in-law were communicated from each village. Therefore, from 30 villages 30 respondents were communicated which arrived at total 900 respondents. The data was substantiated with an analysis of policy instruments, programmes, legal provisions, enforcement machinery, media inputs, etc. on the issue, using secondary source data. Care was taken to maintain confidentiality at all costs.

The Study Region:

The district under study is flanked by the Satpura ranges to the north and Ajanta hills to the south and the central part of the district is covered by well-known Tapi river basin which flows towards the west. The region experiences slightly different climate than by rest of the state of Maharashtra, since it is located away from the coast but at much

lower altitude than the rest of the plateau of Maharashtra. The location away from the coast has resulted in high range of mean daily temperature

which is slightly than 15°C. Low altitude has resulted in abnormally high maximum summer temperature which is normally above 40°C.

Map No.1

The district is bounded by the state of Madhya Pradesh to the north. The rivers Anner and Panjhara form a boundary in the west between the region and the Dhule district. In the east, the district under study is bordered by Buldhana district. To the south, Satmala, Ajantha and Chandor hills form a natural boundary between the study region and the districts of Nasik and Aurangabad. The Jalgaon district which is one of the 34 districts of Maharashtra lies between 20° N and 21° N latitudes and 74° 55' E and 76° 28' E longitudes. The total area of the district is 11765.0 sq. Km. According to 2011 Census, the total population of the region was 42, 29, 917.

Results and Discussion:

The table shows the opinions of respondents on various issues regarding social taboos related to girl and boy. The issues which are commonly follow by the people in the society of the study region are given in the table. The responses regarding these assumptions are taken as 'agree' or 'disagree'. Those who are not confirmed about their opinion come under 'partially agree'. The

analysis of opinions on various issues is as follows.

(i) By birth girls are stronger : A majority of the respondents have reported opinion as disagree. About 40 percent respondents are disagree. Among them, proportion of men is more, i.e. 49 percent. But about 37 percent mother-in-law are agreed on this issue. The women are also inclined towards the opinion that by birth girls are not stronger.

(ii) Is it all right if girls do not go to school? : This is very good indication that from the opinions all the respondents that almost all agree that the girls should go to school. Very few respondents have opinion that it is all right if girls do not go to school, and majority them are mother-in-laws. The respondents have opinion that education is must for girls too.

(iii) Boys need more food than girls : On this issue also a majority of the respondents are disagree that boys need more food. Here quality of food was also included. More than 90 percent respondents disagreed on this issue.

(iv) **Girls should not be allowed to play outside as it is not safe** : This issue is related to safety and security of girls. But more than 75 percent respondent were disagree on this issue, and therefore, they were of the opinion that girls should allowed to play outside and it is safe. However, more than 15 percent respondents were agreed on this issue and reported as it is not safe to allow girls to play outside.

This is also an issue related to the safety and security of older girls. Therefore, there were mixed opinions of the respondents on this issue. About 44 percent respondents were agree that older girls should remain indoor for the purpose of safety and security. But it is also interesting that about 50 percent respondents have opinion that girls and boys are equal and therefore, older girls should not remain indoor.

(v) **Older girls should remain indoors** :

Table No. 01 : Opinions of Respondents on Various Issues

Awareness about Various Issues	Respondents			Total n=900 No. (%)
	Men n=300 No. (%)	Women n=300 No. (%)	Mothers in- Law n=300 No. (%)	
By birth girls are stronger				
Agree	78 (26.0)	90 (30.0)	112 (37.3)	280 (31.1)
Partially agree	75 (25.0)	110 (36.7)	77 (25.7)	262 (29.1)
Disagree	147 (49.0)	100 (33.3)	111 (37.0)	358 (39.8)
It is all right if girls do not go to school				
Agree	07 (2.3)	17 (5.7)	25 (8.3)	49 (5.4)
Partially agree	02 (0.7)	01 (0.3)	01 (0.3)	04 (0.4)
Disagree	291(97.0)	282 (94.0)	274 (91.4)	847 (94.2)
Boys need more food than girls				
Agree	05 (1.7)	03 (1.0)	04 (1.3)	12 (1.3)
Partially agree	41 (13.7)	18 (6.0)	13 (4.3)	72 (8.0)
Disagree	254 (84.6)	279 (93.0)	283 (94.4)	816 (90.7)
Girls should not be allowed to play outside as it is not safe				
Agree	25 (8.3)	51 (17.0)	62 (20.7)	138 (15.3)
Partially agree	35 (11.7)	24 (8.0)	21 (7.0)	80 (8.9)
Disagree	240 (80.0)	225 (75.0)	217 (72.3)	682 (75.8)
Older girls should remain indoors				
Agree	105 (35.0)	134 (44.7)	156 (52.0)	395 (43.9)
Partially agree	16 (5.3)	25 (8.3)	19 (6.3)	60 (6.7)
Disagree	179 (59.7)	141 (47.0)	125 (41.7)	445 (49.4)
Boys are more intelligent than girls				
Agree	07 (2.3)	11 (3.7)	12 (4.0)	30 (3.3)
Partially agree	17 (5.7)	15 (5.0)	08 (2.7)	40 (4.4)
Disagree	276 (92.0)	274 (91.3)	280 (93.3)	830 (92.2)
It is acceptable if a man beats his wife				
Agree	10 (3.3)	05 (1.7)	09 (3.0)	24 (2.7)
Partially agree	12 (4.0)	10 (3.3)	12 (4.0)	34 (3.8)
Disagree	278 (92.7)	285 (95.0)	279 (93.0)	842 (93.6)
Males and females should get equal pay for equal work				
Agree	288 (96.0)	290 (96.6)	278 (92.6)	856 (95.1)
Partially agree	05 (1.7)	05 (1.7)	02 (0.7)	12 (1.3)
Disagree	07 (2.3)	05 (1.7)	20 (6.7)	32 (3.6)
Household work should also be done by males				
Agree	218 (72.7)	222 (74.0)	208 (69.3)	648 (72.0)
Partially agree	57 (19.0)	65 (21.7)	66 (22.0)	188 (20.9)
Disagree	25 (8.3)	13 (4.3)	26 (8.7)	64 (7.1)

Source : Data collected during field work.

Fig. No. 02

Fig. No. 03

Fig. No. 04

(vi) **Boys are more intelligent than girls** : This issue seems to be illogical but included to know the opinions of the respondents. As expected, more than 92 percent respondents were disagree that boys are more intelligent than girls. They are of the opinion that if equal opportunity is provided to boys and girls, girls will prove their intelligence.

(vii) **It is acceptable if a man beats his wife** : The opinions of the respondents on this issue were in favour of women. More than 93 percent respondents not accepted that a man should beat his wife. But it is also interesting that more than 3 percent still accept that a man should beat his wife and it is acceptable.

(viii) **Males and females should get equal pay for equal work** : More than 95 percent respondents agreed on the issue that males and females should get equal pay for equal work. But still there were about 3.6 percent respondents who responded that males should get more pay for equal work.

(ix) **Household work should also be done by males** : It is interesting to know that more than 72 males agreed with the issue that household work should also be done by males. They are helping or ready to help to female house member in household work. But less than 70 percent mother-in-laws are agreed with this opinion.

Fig. No. 05

Fig. No. 06

Fig. No. 07

Fig. No. 08

Fig. No. 09

Fig. No. 10

Conclusion :

The salient finding of the study regarding this issue is that the responses were those that were socially acceptable. But on two issues, namely 'girls should not be allowed to play outside as it is not safe' and 'older girls should remain indoors' the older and more empowered women and the mothers-in-law agreed more vehemently than the men. In fact, mothers-in-law were of the very firm opinion that 'girls should remain indoors' which is not shared so much by the women respondents. Another opinion that goes in favour of women is that a large proportion of respondents 'disagree' with a man beating his wife.

Another pointer is that a sizeable proportion of men are agree which is also a pleasing fact. But still there are some respondents who either 'disagree' or 'partially agree' that household work should be shared by men. It is also interesting that many respondent still are unaware about biological fact that by birth girls are stronger than boys. About 40.0 percent respondents are disagree on the fact that by birth girls are stronger than boys. When the mindset is such that women have to be subordinated, it will be a difficult task, if not impossible to confront it, to bring about any change. Though there are certain good changes happened in the society regarding empowerment of women and girl child but during the field visit, male respondents were vacillating regarding acceptance.

References :

1. Chandana, R. C (2011) : 'Geography of Population : Concepts, Determinants and

Patterns', Kalyani Publishers, Mumbai, pp. 287-288.

2. Ghosh, Esther A. Goel Rita and Shanti Balda (2005) : Awareness of Rural Couples about Sex Ratio. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 2005, 18(2), pp. 167- 68.
3. India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare and Third World Centre for Comparative Studies (2002) : Missing Girls: A Study of Declining Sex Ratio in the Age Group 0-6 Years (A Case Study of Delhi). New Delhi, the author, pp. 160.
4. Nayar, Usha (1995) : Doomed before Birth: Study of Declining Sex Ratio in the Age Group 0-6 Years in Selected Districts of Punjab and Haryana. New Delhi, NCERT, Department of Women's Studies, pp. 287.
5. Prasad, Shweta (2001): Female Foeticide: A Study of Varanasi. Lucknow, Centre for Women's Studies and Development, pp. 14.
6. Yadav, S. S. and Badri, V. S. (1997): Gender Preference and Anxiety of Pregnant Women. Bangalore, Population Centre, pp. 10-14.
7. International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS), Mumbai (2007): National Family Health Survey (NFHS-3) 2005-06. Mumbai, IIPS.
8. National Institute of Public Cooperation and Child Development (2008): A Report on 'A Socio-cultural Study of the Declining Sex Ratio in Delhi and Haryana', Ministry of Women & Child Development, Government of India.
9. <https://factly.in/the-beti-issuse-declining-child-sex-ratio/>